
DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A REALISTIC ELECTRIC BOILER MODEL FOR APPLICATION IN EMS SOFTWARE

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Abstract

In this work a general model to predict the State of Charge (SOC) for electric boilers, is developed and validated. The model is to be implemented and used in an energy management control and simulation toolkit. The model requires minimal computational power and is accurate within normal operating boundaries (1-0.2 SOC). The model is tested using simulation and validated using data obtained from measurements on an actual electric boiler under lab conditions. The predicted behaviour of the model matches calculations from measurements with a maximum difference in SOC of 3% per charging cycle.

1 Introduction

Demand management using demand response and load shifting is a solution to the current grid congestion problem in the Netherlands. For load shifting, models to shift charging electric boilers (E-boilers) in time need to be developed. The model presented in this work is simple, requires little processing power, and takes into account a possible preheating stage.

An E-boiler is a buffer tank filled with water, heated by an electric heating element employing resistive heating. As the water heats, a separation into layers with different temperatures due to density variations emerges, this is called thermal stratification. A boiler takes advantage of thermal stratification by heating water at the bottom and extracting water from the top layer. Since little mixing occurs during the first 80% of the hot water volume, this portion can be discharged without a significant drop in temperature [1]–[3], resulting in a linear decrease in SOC [1].

Simplifications to the thermal gradient in an E-boiler can be made within its normal operating range (SOC 1-0.2) due to its linear behaviour and the formation of distinct zones, the hot, transition, and cold zone [1], [2]. The temperatures in these zones can be approximated as linear, and the gradients in the hot and cold zones can be treated as constant. The transition zone, however, introduces complexity. To simplify, it can be combined into a mixed layer with an average temperature, $T_{cold+transition}$. This approach results in two distinct volumes, each with an average temperature. In reality, under steady-state conditions, there are two layers with a temperature gradient at their intersection.

In this work, two general equations are used for energy in a volume of water (equation 1) and for heat loss from a volume of water (equation 2).

$$E_x = \rho \cdot V_x \cdot c_p \cdot (T_x - T_{reference}) \quad (1)$$

$$E_{heatloss_x} = A_{V_x} \cdot U_x \cdot (T_x - T_y) \cdot t \quad (2)$$

Where E is energy, ρ is the density of water, V is a volume, c_p is the specific heat capacity, T is temperature, A_V is the outside area of a volume V , U is the overall heat transfer coefficient and t is the elapsed time.

Effective load shifting in E-boilers requires accurate determination of the stored thermal energy to ensure an uninterrupted supply of hot water for residents. For this, the SOC is used. $SOC \in [0, 1]$ represents the state of charge of the E-boiler, where SOC indicates the proportion of stored energy relative to its maximum capacity (equation 3).

$$SOC = \frac{E_{total}}{E_{max}} = \frac{E_{V1} + E_{V2}}{E_{max}} \quad (3)$$

To determine E_{total} , an iterative linear model is used. This method provides a balance between accuracy and low computational power [4]. The iterative linear method approach involves tracking the energy balance at each timestep, where the total energy in the boiler is the energy from the previous timestep and the change in energy during the current timestep (equation 4).

$$E_{total} = E_{total_{-1}} + E_{water\ in} + E_{charging} - E_{heatloss} - E_{waterout} \quad (4)$$

Due to the 2 distinct volumes, the energy of each volume needs to be tracked individually, as can be seen in Figure 1. The total energy in the boiler is the

sum of the two volumes. The inlet temperature, elevated due to preheating, and the higher temperature in the “cold” volume is accounted for to track the boiler’s energy. Consequently, this necessitates rewriting the energy balance equations for the boiler (see equations 5 & 6).

$$E_{V1} = E_{V1-1} + E_{\text{water-out}} - E_{\text{heatloss1}} - E_{\text{heatloss3}} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{V2} = E_{V2-1} + E_{\text{water in}} + E_{\text{charging}} + E_{\text{heatloss3}} - E_{\text{heatloss2}} - E_{\text{wateroutcold}} \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. Energy balance of the E-boiler, where V_1 indicates the hot volume and V_2 indicates the cold volume.

To determine $E_{\text{water in}}$, the temperature, T_{inlet} is used, and to determine $E_{\text{water out}}$, the temperature, T_{outlet} is used. The volume of water entering and exiting the boiler is the same and can be indicated by V_{flow} . Energy loss to the environment in volumes V_1 and V_2 is calculated using a general heat transfer coefficient for the boiler, U_{boiler} , as per the general heat loss equation (equation 2). Heat transfer between layers, known as thermocline heat transfer, is usually governed by fluid flow. With limited boiler flow, it can be simplified using the standard heat loss equation [5]. The used heat transfer coefficient experimentally determined by Szczeciński, et al. is $U_{\text{thermocline}} = 0.193 \text{ [W/m}^2 \cdot \text{K]}$ [5].

The resistive heating element heats the water at the bottom of the boiler. As the water heats up, it rises, creating a flow. The cold water gradually heats homogeneously until its temperature matches the temperature of the hot water [1]. Once the temperatures are equal, the entire water volume is homogeneously heated [1]. The model combines the hot and cold water into a single hot water volume when their temperatures match.

2 Results & Discussion

To validate the results, a digital simulation is used and compared with models from literature. Subsequently, the model will be tested in the laboratory, with the testing methodology explained for each section.

2.1 Digital simulation

To assess the behaviour of the model, the result was compared with a simpler linear iterative model using the same simulation approach. A SOC plot for the typical daily demand pattern of a 4-person household with an annual domestic hot water energy demand of 9 GJ/year was used for comparison [1]. The demand pattern is given in L/h of 40°C water. The modelled thermal storage has a capacity of 200L and is heated to 60°C [1].

Comparing the SOC plot from van Leeuwen [1] with the plot generated using the boiler model (using van Leeuwen’s data) shows similar results, with an accumulated discrepancy in SOC over an entire day of 3% (see Figure 2). The boiler model should be improved by taking into account heat loss, with two separate heat loss equations for V_1, V_2 and heat diffusion in the boiler. Although heat diffusion in the boiler does not directly affect SOC, it influences the external heat loss and the temperature of V_1 and V_2 .

Fig. 2. Typical hot water demand pattern and the resulting SOC from the boiler model, with and without heat loss, compared to the reference SOC from van Leeuwen (dashed line) [1].

For heat transfer, a heat transfer coefficient for the boiler is required. For a 200L E-boiler with 40mm insulation [6], taking a standard insulation material, PUR insulation foam (0.03 [W/(m · K)] [7]), the general heat transfer coefficient is 0.75 [W/(m² · K)]. Taking into account heat loss results in an overall height difference, leading to an 8% discrepancy in SOC over a full day.

In conclusion: The model aligns with and enhances the behaviour of similar tested and validated models from the literature.

2.1 Laboratory validation

To validate the model against a real-world boiler, a test setup with two 80L E-boilers (TESY BiLight inox slim 80 SSV 803520 B12 TSRC) is used. One boiler is equipped with five temperature sensors (Endress+Hauser Easytemp TMR31 class A Pt100), spaced at roughly equal intervals along its height (see Figure 3). The sensors are connected to a data logger (Model DT85) to synchronize the time steps.

Fig. 3: Schematic overview of the boiler validation test setup, with the indicated components and sensors.

To initialize the model, attributes such as the location of the temperature sensors, tank dimensions and overall heat transfer coefficient must be determined. All of these can be inferred from the physical boiler, except the heat transfer coefficient. To find U_{boiler} , the boiler temperature was monitored over several days while the boiler was first fully charged and then unplugged. Because of the non-linear temperature gradient when the boiler is fully charged (the water volume below the heating element is not heated to the same temperature as the rest of the boiler), a weighted average temperature was determined.

The weighted average is calculated by dividing the boiler into volumes with average temperatures and taking each volume's percentage of the total volume. This gives the following volume fractions:

$$a = 0.195, b = 0.193, c = 0.211, d = 0.218, e = 0.183$$

$$T_{weighted avg.} = a \cdot T_1 + b \cdot T_2 + c \cdot T_3 + d \cdot T_4 + e \cdot T_5 \quad (7)$$

The temperature readings for each sensor over time are plotted (Figure 4), and the theoretical temperature decrease, based on the heatloss equation, is fitted to the weighted average temperature plot, $T_{weighted avg.}$ (equation 7). The fitted heat transfer coefficient is $U_{boiler} = 1.58 \text{ [W/(m}^2 \cdot \text{K)]}$.

Fig. 4: Plotted temperature sensor data from T_1 to T_5 , $T_{weighted avg.}$, and the temperature decrease predicted by the model with the fitted heat transfer coefficient, $U_{boiler} = 1.58 \text{ W/(m}^2 \cdot \text{K)}$.

With all boiler characteristics determined, the SOC can be determined. The boiler is equipped with 5 temperature sensors, providing temperature data at different heights (Figure 4). It is assumed that temperature differences primarily occur along the height due to radial symmetry and thermal stratification [1], [2]. However, the temperature gradient between two sensors remains unknown, as explained previously the temperature gradient is assumed to be linear in most regions, except at transitions between linear sections, such as from the thermocline from the hot to the cold zone. To determine the SOC using the boiler volumes and the 5 temperature sensors, it is necessary to identify the height and location of the thermocline, as well as its behaviour during operation.

To determine the thermocline height and its behaviour during operation, the boiler was fully charged and then emptied with a constant outflow volume. The temperatures recorded by the sensors were logged and plotted over time. A time interval was identified

during which the thermocline (defined as the thermal gradient between 70°C and 25°C) passed each sensor. By using the time it takes for the thermocline to pass each sensor and the outflow rate, the thermocline height can be determined. With the thermocline height known, the energy in the boiler and the SOC can be calculated.

Outflow speed significantly affects the thermocline at the bottom of the boiler. At higher outflow speeds, such as 15 L/min, there is considerable mixing at the bottom of the boiler. However, this speed exceeds the expected maximum outflow rate. At more realistic outflow speeds, like 5 L/min, less mixing occurs, resulting in a more stable thermocline at the bottom of the boiler.

With known thermocline behaviour at an outflow speed of 5 L/min, the fully charged E-boiler was discharged in 6 steps, with periods of no discharge to allow the sensor readings to stabilize. This created 6 points in time (t1-t6) at which the SOC could be calculated (Figure 5). To calculate the SOC at these moments (t1-t6), the boiler is divided into sections of different volumes at each time step, with the thermocline as one of the volumes. The temperature at each sensor is taken as the average temperature for its respective volume, allowing the energy in each volume to be calculated (equation 1). Summing up the energy of all volumes provides the amount of energy in the boiler (equation 8).

Fig. 5. Data from the temperature sensors T_1 - T_5 and the outflow temperature, T_{outlet} , with the indicated time points t1-t6.

$$E_{t_x} = \sum \left(\frac{h_n}{h_{total}} \cdot V_{total} \cdot \rho \cdot c_p \cdot (T_{avg_n} - T_{reference}) \right) \quad (8)$$

With 6 moments in time, there will be 6 amounts of energy at each moment (t1-t6), denoted by E_{t1} to E_{t6} , where $E_{t1} = E_{max}$. To calculate E_{t_x} , the heights of the volumes must first be determined. This is done by dividing the boiler into 5 volumes, with each T_x being in the middle of a volume so that the sensor temperature represents the average temperature for that volume.

The thermocline is taken as the volume for one of the sensors, and the leftover volume (due to the thermocline being smaller than the volumes of water in which the sensor is in the middle) are combined with the volumes above and below (see Figure 6). The size of the added leftover volume to the volumes above and below are calculated based on the temperature of the sensor reading at the location of the thermocline. Doing this for each moment in time and using E_{t1} as E_{max} to calculate the SOC, gives table 1.

Table 1: Calculating the SOC for the six moments, E_{t1} - E_{t6}

	E_{t1}	E_{t2}	E_{t3}	E_{t4}	E_{t5}	E_{t6}
E [kJ]	20224.7	15810.6	11989.5	8059.2	4405.9	1398.7
SOC	1.00	0.78	0.59	0.40	0.22	0.07

The model is run using external sensor readings (not the sensors inside the boiler, T_1 - T_5). However, the model does only partially account for heat diffusion within the boiler due to mass flow, leading to a discrepancy between the energy and the volume of hot water. To address this, the model sets the energy in the volume to zero, causing a sudden drop in SOC, as shown in Figure 7. This results in less energy leaving the boiler than predicted, due to internal heat loss to cooler water layers, slightly overestimating the SOC.

Fig. 6. Schematic heat distribution at a moment t2 in the E-boiler, indicated in red (high temperature) and white (low temperature).

However, the lack of internal heat transfer from mass flow does not limit the model's applicability to standard control situations, where the boiler is always

expected to have a little bit of hot water available. This ensures charging occurs at or above the 0.2 SOC threshold, below which the SOC calculation becomes highly inaccurate.

Fig. 7. The SOC model uses sensor data of the outflow, and inlet and outlet temperatures. Mixing is not included leading to strange behaviour below 20% SOC.

In conclusion: Within the 1-0.2 SOC range, the model shows a 1% discrepancy compared with calculations from measured data, indicating that neglecting heat transfer due to mass flow does not significantly affect accuracy. This discrepancy can be reduced by recalibrating the model after each charging cycle, setting the SOC to 1 after completing a charging cycle.

3 Conclusion & Future work

The SOC model is simple yet accurate, showing only a 1% discrepancy over a full discharge cycle when compared to sensor-based SOC calculations. However, our calculations indicate a slight overestimation of the SOC. This model requires minimal computational power while remaining accurate enough to provide a reliable indication of the boiler's state.

Based on the high accuracy of the predictions, the model allows to shift loads by the E-boiler with great certainty. This leads to a higher degree of self-utilization of generated solar power and can mitigate grid congestion when implemented. Additionally, it can advocate for the use of E-boilers when combined with self-generated electricity sources and load shifting.

Ongoing future work consists of a further exploration of higher inlet temperatures (simulating a preheating stage in the form of a water buffer or solar thermal panels) effect on the model. Further measurements and investigation into the effects of outflow speed and its effect on heat diffusion in the boiler would help validate the model for a broader range of applications.

4 Acknowledgements

This study is part of the SERENE and SUSTENANCE projects, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 957682 and No 101022587, respectively.

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